

THERMOPLASTIC MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR STRUCTURAL AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT: This paper first discusses the issues related to the application of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites in automotive body and chassis structures. They are related to both properties and processing of thermoplastic matrix composites. It then presents elevated temperature tension data of E-glass and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene and polyamide-6 composites that may be useful for designing beam-type components for automotive applications.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic matrix composites, automotive applications, tensile modulus, tensile strength, elevated temperature effect

INTRODUCTION

Over the last two decades, the automobile industry has been pursuing a variety of technological developments and design strategies to meet increasingly stringent automobile performance requirements in the areas of fuel economy and emissions. Among these, the reduction of vehicle weight has proved to be particularly effective. Vehicle weight reduction can be achieved in a variety of ways, such as vehicle downsizing, redesigning the vehicle architecture (e.g., using space frame structure instead of traditional body-in-white structure), using lightweight materials, redesigning existing components with thinner gage sheets and reducing the number of components. One major option in the vehicle weight reduction strategy is the use of lightweight materials, namely aluminum alloys, magnesium alloys and fiber-reinforced polymers. Substantial research and development has already taken place in all these categories of materials. While the nonferrous alloys, especially 5xxx and 6xxx series aluminum alloys, are finding increasing use in automotive structures and have been the focus of attention in recently developed PNGV vehicles, the use of fiber-reinforced polymers in automotive structures has been very limited for a number of reasons. Included among them are the lack of long-term property data and the lack of design experience in the automotive environment. One other major factor is the long processing time with thermosetting matrix composites, which is one of the reasons for their high processing cost relative to conventional stamping operation used for steel and aluminum alloys.

The attention in the automotive industry thus far has been on thermosetting matrix composites, such as polyesters, vinyl esters and polyurethanes. The manufacturing processes used with these materials are compression molding, resin transfer molding and structural reaction injection molding. While much research has been done to develop these processes as well as products using these processes, most of the thermosetting matrix composites considered for structural applications are not cost-competitive with steel and aluminum alloys because of their long processing time.

Thermoplastic matrix composites are comparable to thermosetting matrix composites in modulus and strength, since they use the same fiber reinforcement, such as glass, carbon and aramid. The difference is in the matrix material, which holds the fibers together. Unlike a thermosetting matrix, a thermoplastic matrix can be repeatedly softened and melted by heat, and therefore can be post-formed.

Among the advantages of using a thermoplastic polymer instead of a thermosetting polymer as the matrix material are improved toughness, recyclability, weldability and shorter processing time [1].

One of the reasons continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites have not received much attention in the past is the difficulty of incorporating continuous fibers in thermoplastic matrix, which is due to its high viscosity. Recently however, a number of processes have been developed that can reduce this difficulty [2, 3] and, in fact, thermoplastic matrix composite prepregs have become commercially available. There are now several applications of thermoplastic matrix composites in aerospace, biomedical and other industries. The thermoplastics used for these applications are polyetherimide (PEI), polyether-ether-ketone (PEEK) and polyphenylene sulfide (PPS). These polymers are selected for these applications primarily for their heat and/or chemical resistance. However, they are also very expensive, and therefore are not suitable for automotive applications. Lower cost thermoplastic polymers, such as polypropylene and polyamides, that are already in use in injection molded parts in automobiles will be ideally suited as the matrix material for structural automotive applications provided the properties obtained from these composites are high enough to compare favorably with steel and aluminum alloys.

Successful application of thermoplastic matrix composites will require that their cost/weight ratio be as competitive as possible with that of steel and aluminum alloys. The cost has two major parts, the material cost and the processing cost. To reduce the material cost, it will be required to use low cost fibers as well as low cost matrix. Reduction in processing cost is as important as reduction in material cost, since they will be in competition with sheet steel that are formed in stamping presses requiring only a few seconds for cycle time.

In this paper, we will first discuss the important issues related to the application of continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites in the automotive industry. Then we will present the tensile properties of continuous glass and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene (PP) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) composites. These materials are commercially available in prepreg form. However, complete characterization of these materials is not available. The experimental data presented here are part of the characterization study needed for greater use of these composites in automotive applications.

ISSUES RELATED TO AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

The two most important issues related to the selection of fiber-reinforced polymers for automotive applications are cost and performance. The cost includes both material cost and manufacturing cost. The material cost includes not only the fiber cost and the matrix cost, but also the preprocessing cost, such as the prepregging cost. While glass fibers have a large cost advantage over carbon fibers and are already used in sheet molding compound (SMC) composites for body panels, it is generally recognized that carbon fibers will be needed to fully utilize the weight saving potential of composites over steel and aluminum alloys. At today's price of carbon fibers, carbon fiber reinforced composites are not cost competitive with steel or aluminum alloys. The matrix cost is also an important consideration, since the composite may contain up to 60 volume percent of matrix. Therefore, a low cost matrix, if it performs well, will be desirable. This is one of the reasons for considering polypropylene and polyamide 6 as the matrix in thermoplastic matrix composites for automotive applications. Typical costs of fibers and thermoplastic polymers considered suitable for structural automotive applications are given in Table 1.

The processing cost of polymer matrix composites includes several factors, such as cycle time, tooling cost, processing equipment cost, etc. While tooling and processing equipment (e.g., press) costs are, in general, lower for composite parts than for either steel or aluminum parts, the cost associated with cycle time can be significantly higher for composite parts. For stamped steel parts, the cycle time is usually in the range of one or more parts per minute. For a thermosetting matrix composite part with

equivalent bending stiffness as that of a steel part, the cycle time can be in the range of 2–5 minutes if a polyester or a vinyl ester resin is used, and 10 minutes or longer if an epoxy resin is used as the matrix. The long cycle time required for the thermosetting matrix composites makes them less competitive with steel parts, except at low production volumes. Thermoplastic matrix composites, on the other hand, can be processed with much shorter cycle time, mainly because no time-dependent chemical reaction is involved during the processing of these composites into the final part. Thus, for example, if press-forming operation is used for processing a thermoplastic matrix composite, the cycle time in the press may be less than a minute.

A number of investigators have considered press forming as an option for high speed processing of thermoplastic matrix composites [4-7]. Recently, Mallick and his co-workers [8, 9] have been exploring the possibility of combining press forming and vibration welding (Fig. 1) to produce polypropylene and polyamide-6 matrix composite beams for automotive applications. They have shown that this process can be very cost-competitive with roll forming process of making steel tubes for a crossbeam application in an automobile. The cost difference-weight difference ratio of a carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene beam compared to a steel beam is shown in Fig. 2. In this case, the weight saving with the composite beam is more than 65%, yet there is substantial cost saving potential even at a carbon fiber price of \$16/kg. The cost saving potential becomes higher over a larger annual production volume as the carbon fiber price is reduced to \$8/kg.

The performance issues related to the automotive application of fiber-reinforced composites include for short- term and long-term mechanical, thermal and environmental properties. They include tensile, compressive, shear, fatigue, impact damage tolerance, creep, etc. Although for initial design purposes, tensile, compressive and shear properties are considered, long-term properties under fatigue and creep loading will be needed for a number of chassis components and body structures. Furthermore, all of these properties must be determined under typical automotive environment, such as salt water, gasoline and automotive fluids. One major concern with thermoplastic matrix composites is the effect of temperature. At elevated temperatures, thermoplastic polymers tend to decrease in both modulus and strength, and at low temperatures, they tend to become brittle. However, the decrease in modulus and strength is significant only if the temperature exceeds the glass transition temperature of the polymer. Even then, the elevated temperature effect is much smaller in semi-crystalline polymers, such as polypropylene and polyamide-6, than in amorphous polymers, such as ABS.

Table 1: Typical Material Properties

Property	Polyamide-6	Polypropylene	Glass Fiber	Carbon Fiber	SAE 1010 Steel (Cold Drawn)	6061-T6 Aluminum Alloy
Density (g/cm ³)	1.13	0.90	2.54	1.8	7.87	2.70
Tensile Strength (MPa)	70-85	21-37	1750	3200	365	310
Tensile Modulus (GPa)	1.4	1.1-1.3	72.4	220	207	69
Relative Cost	7	1.5	2.5	300	1	3.5

Figure 1: Steps in manufacturing full beam sections of thermoplastic matrix composites using a combination of press forming and vibration welding.

Figure 2: Cost difference /weight difference ratio between a steel beam and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene (CFPP) beam.

TENSILE CHARACTERISTICS OF PP AND PA-6 MATRIX COMPOSITES

In this section, we will report the tensile characteristics of several glass and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene (PP) and polyamide-6 (PA-6) composite laminates at three different temperatures, namely 23, 50 and 100°C. Three types of continuous fiber reinforcements were considered for the PP matrix composites, namely unidirectional E-glass fibers, unidirectional carbon fibers and balanced bi-directional E-glass fabric. For the PA-6 matrix composites, the reinforcements were unidirectional E-glass fibers and unidirectional carbon fibers. All unidirectional prepregs were obtained from Baycomp. Several $[0]$, $[0/90/0]_s$ and $[90/0/90]_s$ laminates were prepared from the unidirectional prepregs using compression molding under heat and pressure. Henceforth, they are referred to as $[0]$, $[0/90]$ and $[90/0]$ laminates. The fabric-reinforced laminate was obtained from Twintex. It was compression molded from commingled glass and polypropylene fibers. The details of the compression molding conditions and tensile tests are available in Ref. 10.

Fig. 3 shows the typical tensile load-displacement diagram obtained for the $[0]$ GF-PP laminates. The decrease in the initial slope and the increase in non-linearity with increasing temperature are evident in this diagram. Tensile modulus and tensile strength values of various laminates molded from the unidirectional fiber prepregs are shown as a function of temperature in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5, respectively. As expected, the $[0]$ laminates had the highest tensile modulus and tensile strength, since the fibers in these laminates were in the loading direction. The $[90/0]$ laminates had all but two layers in the transverse direction, i.e., 90° to the loading direction. Thus, these laminates had the lowest tensile modulus and tensile strength, and for all practical purposes, these properties can be assumed to be the transverse tensile properties of the material. On the other hand, the tensile properties of the $[0]$ laminates are the longitudinal properties. The $[0/90]$ laminates exhibited tensile modulus and tensile strength either close to $[0]$ laminates or intermediate between the $[0]$ and $[90/0]$ laminates. It can also be observed from Figs. 4 and 5 that the increasing the temperature from 23 to 100°C had the greatest deleterious effect on the properties of the $[90/0]$ laminates, since these properties are more matrix dominated due to the presence of mostly 90° layers. Using the measured fiber volume fraction and fiber tensile modulus from the literature [1], it is possible to predict the longitudinal tensile modulus of each material and compare it with experimentally determined tensile modulus. Since the matrix modulus is very small compared to the fiber modulus, its contribution to the longitudinal modulus can be neglected so that $E_{11} = \text{Longitudinal modulus} \approx E_f v_f$. Using this equation and assuming the glass fiber modulus as 70 GPa, the theoretical longitudinal modulus of the glass fiber reinforced PP and PA-6 composites is 21.7 GPa, which is very close to the experimental values of 19.5 and 23.1 GPa, respectively. However, a similar calculation for carbon fiber composites predicts the theoretical modulus values are higher than the experimental values. An examination of the carbon fiber composite specimens showed that the fiber orientation in these specimens were between 1-5° off from the longitudinal direction, which explains their lower than the theoretical values.

Fig. 6 shows the tensile modulus vs. temperature and tensile strength vs. temperature for the balanced bi-directional fabric reinforced polypropylene laminates. In this case, the 0 and 90 direction properties were nearly equal, since the fabric was balanced. Both tensile modulus and tensile strength decreased with increasing temperature, but the decrease was greater for the modulus than for the strength.

CONCLUSIONS

The experimental results presented here show that the tensile modulus and tensile strength of glass and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene and polyamide-6 composites decrease with increasing temperature. However, the extent of decrease depends on the fiber orientation relative to the loading direction. The

elevated temperature properties are one of many other properties that will be needed for these composites to be accepted in the automotive industry.

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Figure 3: Tensile load vs. displacement diagrams of [0] GF-PP laminates at 23°C (room temperature),

50°C and 100°C test temperatures

Figure 4: Tensile modulus vs. temperature for different glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene and polyamide-6 laminates. They are designated as GF-PP, CF-PP, GF-PA6 and CF-PA6, respectively.

Figure 5: Tensile strength vs. temperature for different glass fiber and carbon fiber reinforced polypropylene and polyamide-6 laminates. They are designated as GF-PP, CF-PP, GF-PA6 and CF-PA6, respectively.

Figure 6: Variation of tensile modulus and tensile strength with temperature of a balanced glass fabric reinforced polypropylene laminate.